

Better overeducated than unemployed?

The short- and long-term effects of an overeducated labor market re-entry

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Acknowledgements

The authors thank Michael Gebel, Bodo Aretz, Andreas Franken, Zerrin Salikutluk, and three anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments and suggestions. We also thank the discussants and participants at the IAB Workshop Quality of Employment in Nuremberg, 2014 and at the 11th International Young Scholar German Socio-Economic Panel Symposium in Delmenhorst, 2015. The data were kindly provided by the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW), Berlin, Germany.

Funding

This work was supported by the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme [FP7/2007-2013, grant agreement number 613257]. This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 649496.

Please note:

This is pre-copyedited, author-produced PDF of an article accepted for publication in *European Sociological Review* following peer review. The version of record “Voßemer, J. and Schuck, B. (2015). Better overeducated than unemployed? The short- and long-term effects of an overeducated labor market re-entry. *European Sociological Review*, 1-15. doi: 10.1093/esr/jcv093” is available at:

<http://esr.oxfordjournals.org/content/early/2015/10/27/esr.jcv093.abstract>

Abstract

Previous studies have shown that overeducation is inferior to adequate employment. For example, overeducated workers have lower earnings, participate less often in continuing education and training, and are less satisfied with their jobs. This article changes perspectives by asking whether it is better for the unemployed to take up a job for which they are overeducated or to remain unemployed and continue the search for adequate employment. Theoretically, we rely on the established confrontation of the stepping stone and trap hypotheses which make opposing predictions in terms of long-term employment chances and job quality. Using the German Socio-Economic Panel (1984-2012) and applying a dynamic propensity score matching approach, the analyses reveal an interesting trade-off. Although an overeducated re-entry increases the long-term employment chances persistently, it also implies strong lock-in effects into overeducation for up to five years after re-employment. In sum, the results support the stepping stone hypothesis in terms of future employment chances, but also highlight non-negligible risks of remaining trapped in a job that is below one's level of educational qualification.

1 Introduction

Numerous studies have shown that overeducation compared to adequate employment is associated with social and economic disadvantages (see McGuinness, 2006 for a review). Being employed in a job below ones level of education translates into lower earnings (Korpi and Tåhlin, 2009), lower chances of participating in continuing education and training (Büchel and Mertens, 2004), and lower job satisfaction (Verhaest and Omey, 2009). Therefore, overeducation is commonly considered inferior to adequate employment. However, comparing overeducation only to adequate employment neglects that it represents an important alternative to unemployment as well. Given the empirical evidence on unemployment scarring in terms of earnings (Gangl, 2006) and job quality (Dieckhoff, 2011), the question arises how overeducation compares to unemployment. We change perspectives and complement previous studies by asking whether it is better for the unemployed to take up a job for which they are overeducated or to remain unemployed and continue the search for adequate employment.

Theoretically, we rely on the established yet undecided confrontation of the stepping stone and trap hypotheses (Baert *et al.*, 2013; Pollmann-Schult and Büchel, 2004a; Scherer, 2004). According to the former an overeducated re-entry increases the chances of both employment per se and adequate employment in the long-run. In contrast, the trap hypothesis states that it is better to decline offers for overeducated jobs and continue the search in order to avoid disadvantages in terms of labor market integration and job quality. Empirical evidence from the few studies with a similar perspective supports the trap hypothesis, but is restricted to graduates (Baert *et al.*, 2013; Scherer, 2004) or unemployed with vocational training (Pollmann-Schult and Büchel, 2004a). We complement these studies by testing the opposing theoretical scenarios for a broader sample of unemployed. However, addressing this research question is not only interesting from a theoretical perspective, but also from a policy point of

view. It informs policy-makers on strategies in fighting unemployment without losing sight of the trade-off between employment and job quality. Should policy-makers enforce acceptance of job offers irrespective of the matching between actual and required qualifications or should they weigh shortened unemployment durations against the potentially negative long-term effects of an overeducated re-entry, in particular, in terms of job quality?

Against this background, our study contributes to the overeducation literature in several ways. Theoretically, we take the widely neglected perspective of comparing an overeducated re-entry to remaining unemployed and continuing the job search. We complement the few previous studies by offering first evidence on the German labor market for all levels of education and labor market experience. Methodologically, we apply a dynamic extension of propensity score matching (Sianesi, 2004) to address the central problem of selection into overeducation. This also allows us to adequately address the problem of choosing an appropriate control group. Furthermore, we analyze the effects of an overeducated re-entry considering both employment chances and the chances of adequate employment. Thereby, we shed light on potential trade-offs or cumulative (dis-)advantages between employment chances and job quality. Lastly, using the German Socio-Economic Panel, we are able to follow the unemployed for up to five years after re-employment allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the short- and long-term effects of an overeducated re-entry. As the predictions of the stepping stone and trap hypotheses only differ in the long-run, a long-term perspective appears to be particularly important.

The remainder of this article proceeds as follows: the next section addresses the question why an overeducated re-entry should be a stepping stone or a trap for the unemployed compared to continuing the search for adequate employment. The following sections present the data, measures, and analytic strategy, followed by a discussion of the results. The last section summarizes the findings and offers some concluding remarks.

2 Theory and hypotheses

Following the overeducation literature, we draw on sociological and economic micro-level theories and derive the opposing stepping stone and trap hypotheses offering a starting point for analyzing the effects of an overeducated re-entry. Unlike previous studies, which usually compare overeducation to adequate employment, the following argumentation focuses on the comparison of an overeducated re-entry to the alternative of remaining unemployed and continuing the job search.

2.1 Why should an overeducated re-entry be a stepping stone for the unemployed?

While overeducation is usually considered detrimental to individuals' careers, changing the reference from adequate employment to unemployment may alter this view. Various theories indicate that taking up an overeducated job out of unemployment may represent a bridge into employment and better jobs. For example, following signaling and statistical discrimination theories, employers may use an individual's work history and job search decisions to overcome the problem of insufficient information on a potential employee's productivity (McCormick, 1990; Korpi and Levin, 2001). Taking up overeducated employment instead of remaining unemployed will be valued positively by prospective employers, since job searchers signal their general motivation, employability, and productivity. In addition, this allows avoiding the stigma effects associated with prolonged unemployment. Recent experimental evidence supports this perspective by suggesting a larger stigma effect of unemployment than overeducation (Baert and Verhaest, 2014).

Social network and job-shopping theory offer another argument in favor of the stepping stone hypothesis highlighting the comparative advantage of an on-the-job search (Granovetter, 1973; Johnson, 1978). These theories emphasize that work experience increases job search effectiveness by giving access to information on better (matching) vacancies. More specific-

ly, social network theory argues that an on-the-job search allows building a social network in the respective company or industry which may be helpful in finding adequate employment. In line with the signaling arguments outlined above, the higher effectiveness of an on-the-job search may also originate from the fact that employers take the current employment status as an important productivity signal for hiring decisions (Pollmann-Schult and Büchel, 2004a). Taken together the access to more and better matching job vacancies should reduce mismatches and subsequent unemployment.

From the perspective of human capital theory, re-entering the labor market in a job for which one is overeducated will also reduce the depreciation of human capital, occupation-specific skills and general employment skills compared to remaining unemployed (Korpi and Levin, 2001). In addition, taking up an overeducated job may not only counteract the depreciation of human capital, but also allow for further investments in human capital, like general employment skills, continuing education and training or work experience. Despite of empirical evidence showing that overeducation is inferior compared to adequate employment in terms of continuing education and training (Büchel and Mertens, 2004), it may provide more and better opportunities than unemployment. Moreover, career mobility theory suggests the enhancement of both internal and external promotion probabilities by rationally choosing overeducation as an investment into work experience (Sicherman and Galor, 1990). Therefore, re-entering the labor market in an overeducated job compared to remaining unemployed and continuing the job search may not only reduce the depreciation of human capital, but also help to maintain and develop it further. In sum, the stepping stone hypothesis links an overeducated re-entry with higher employment chances and higher job quality in the long-run.

Hypothesis 1a: Taking up an overeducated job compared to remaining unemployed will increase future employment chances and chances of adequate employment.

2.2 Why should an overeducated re-entry be a trap for the unemployed?

In contrast to the argumentation above, re-entering the labor market via overeducated employment may just as well turn out to be a long-term trap, for example, by retarding transitions to adequate employment (Baert *et al.*, 2013). In the following we will sketch relevant mechanisms challenging the positive implications of the stepping stones hypothesis.

Taking up an overeducated job may as well be perceived as a bad signal by employers and thus negatively affect the advancement to better jobs as well as the long-term employment prospects. Referring to unemployed skilled workers, McCormick (1990: 311) argues that “low investment in search for another skilled job is used by firms as a productivity signal.” Forgiving the chance of adequate employment by re-entering the labor market into overeducation may accordingly cause serious doubts about an unemployed skilled worker’s productivity and professional aspirations.

Coupled with the uncertainty about the direction of the signaling effects, some researchers also challenge the presumed comparative advantage of searching on-the-job. For example, Baert *et al.* (2013) argue that the job search intensity while searching on-the-job will hardly be comparable to an off-the-job search. Given that search intensity and success are positively related, the overeducated re-entry may be disadvantageous compared to remaining unemployed and searching off-the-job by retarding the search for adequate employment.

As for the human capital development, it was argued above that taking up an overeducated job may prevent the depreciation of human capital that is associated with unemployment. However, the overeducated re-entry could also be disadvantageous if the acquisition of job-specific human capital constitutes a long-term mobility barrier. Investing in specific skills by on-the-job training may lock employees into their suboptimal employment positions (Pissarides, 1994) and retard the advancement to adequate employment, whereas remaining

unemployed always entails the possibility of directly finding an adequate job. In addition, according to the “use-it-or-loose-it” principle overeducated employees will soon adapt to their lower job requirements and thereby lose cognitive abilities (Grip *et al.*, 2007), whereas waiting for an adequate job offer still entails the chance of using one’s skills adequately shortly after. In sum, these arguments imply that overeducated re-employment represents a trap involving lower employment chances and lower chances of advancement to adequate employment.

Hypothesis 1b: Re-entering the labor market in an overeducated job compared to remaining unemployed will decrease future employment chances and chances of adequate employment.

2.3 Effect heterogeneity

Up to now our confrontation of the stepping stone and trap hypotheses has been relatively general although previous findings suggest that the effects of an overeducated re-entry compared to remaining unemployed differ across the unemployed (Baert *et al.*, 2013). In particular, we expect the effects to vary by labor market experience and educational qualifications.

First, we expect different effects for workers in their early career and established workers based on the assumption that information problems will be more relevant for the former (Korpi and Levin, 2001). Since early career workers lack important productivity indicators like past employment history or employer references, their possibilities in signaling high productivity are very limited compared to established workers. Acquiring work experience therefore is rational for them (Sicherman and Galor, 1990), whereas workers with a long employment history and references from former positions can also make use of other productivity indicators. Additionally, overeducation in the early employment career may have a very

different meaning than in later career phases. Considering the early career as an ongoing matching process, episodes of overeducation should not result in a stigma effect for workers at the beginning of their career. Accordingly, the unemployed in their early career are expected to benefit more from an overeducated re-entry into the labor market than those who have already acquired a lot of labor market experience.

Hypothesis 2: Unemployed in their early career should benefit more from an overeducated re-entry into the labor market than unemployed in their mid- and late-career.

Second, we expect different effects for individuals with vocational and academic qualifications assuming that an overeducated re-entry represents a worse signal for the former than for the latter. Two arguments support this view. First, for unemployed with vocational degrees overeducation is by definition associated with completely unskilled positions. In contrast, unemployed with academic qualifications still often hold skilled positions. The greater descent experienced by those with vocational qualifications likely conveys a worse signal to future employers than the one sent by unemployed with academic qualifications. Second, an overeducated re-entry of those with vocational degrees may also send adverse signals, because they accept an unskilled position despite having an occupation-specific training. This may, however, be more important for those unemployed with less other signals, like for example, work experience. In sum, we expect an overeducated re-entry to be a worse signal for unemployed with vocational degrees than for unemployed with academic qualifications meaning that an overeducated re-entry is associated with more positive effects for the latter than for the former.

Hypothesis 3: Unemployed with academic qualifications should benefit more from an overeducated re-entry into the labor market than unemployed with vocational degrees.

3 Data and Methods

3.1 Data and sample selection

We draw on data from the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) for the period 1984 to 2012. The SOEP is designed to be nationally representative of German households and offers panel data on the individual and household level. It provides information on persons' education and labor market behavior as well as retrospective data on their monthly employment status (Wagner *et al.*, 2007). Based on the yearly and monthly data we create an inflow sample into unemployment following the unemployed for up to five years after re-employment. Left-censored spells have been excluded.¹ The sample is restricted to persons of age 18-54 who experience at least one month of unemployment between 1984 and 2011. Because respondents may report more than one employment status in each month, we use a state space to define their main employment status. Additionally, persons without a vocational or university degree can by definition not be overeducated and are excluded from the analyses. To further reduce the heterogeneity among the unemployed, we only focus on those who have lost their job. Applying these restrictions we observe 4,538 person-spells from 3,353 persons including 1,067 exits into overeducation.

3.2 Measures

Overeducation

The treatment of interest is exiting unemployment into a job for which one is overeducated. Overeducation is the extent to which a worker's level of education exceeds the level that is typically required for their particular job (McGuinness, 2006). To measure overeducation we rely on the so-called subjective approach. The SOEP contains yearly information about a worker's highest educational qualification and the qualifications typically needed for their current job. Comparing a worker's educational qualification with the reported level of re-

quired education generates a vertical mismatch variable distinguishing between adequate employment and overeducation. Compared to other measurements the subjective approach has the advantage of “obtaining information from the source closest to the actual job situation, taking account of all specific circumstances” (Hartog and Oosterbeek, 1988: 186).² However, it also has been criticized for its subjectivity, for example, allowing persons to under- or overstate the level of education typically required. For this reason, we adopt an extension of the subjective approach proposed by Büchel and Weißhuhn (1998). This approach validates workers’ subjective assessments by reference to information about their occupational status. A detailed description of the measurement model is given in Supplement A. The validation of the standard subjective measurement results in two additional categories that have to be excluded from the analyses: implausible combinations (about 2%) and degree of mismatch not clearly determinable (about 8%). However, the major advantage of the extended subjective approach is its higher validity by drawing a sharper line between adequate employment and overeducation. Some re-entries may be misclassified because the measurement is based on the yearly data and the mismatch status may have changed between the month of exiting unemployment and the next yearly interview. However, the number of misclassifications is likely to be low.³

Employment chances and job quality

To provide a balanced picture of the effects of an overeducated re-entry, we consider the following two outcomes. First, we measure the probability of being employed, irrespective of educational (mis-)match (1=employed, 0=not employed). This outcome is measured every 6 months up to 60 months after exiting unemployment. Although it indicates a worker’s short- and long-term employment chances, it does not consider subsequent job quality. An objective measure of job quality is the chance of adequate employment (1=adequately employed, 0=overeducated). This outcome is measured annually one to five years after an overeducated

re-entry. Analyzing both employment chances and the chances of adequate employment is important to highlight potential trade-offs or cumulative (dis-)advantages. For example, an overeducated re-entry may increase the unemployed's labor market integration in the long-run without being a stepping stone into adequate employment.

3.3 Methods

To assess the effects of an overeducated re-entry compared to remaining unemployed and continuing the job search, we apply a dynamic propensity score matching approach (Sianesi, 2004). It extends propensity score matching to a dynamic setting taking account of the time-varying treatment. Instead of defining the controls as those who never take up an overeducated job, it defines them as those unemployed who do not experience the treatment until a certain point in time. Simply using the first definition may bias the results, because it conditions on future outcomes. For example, if the reason for never taking up an overeducated job is that an unemployed has found adequate employment before, the estimates will be biased towards negative treatment effects (Caliendo, 2006).

For this reason, the treatment is defined by taking up an overeducated job after an elapsed unemployment duration u ($D^{(u)} = 1$, treated) compared to remaining unemployed and continuing the search for at least one month ($D^{(u)} = 0$, controls).⁴ The observed outcomes of interest – future employment chances and chances of adequate employment – are defined over time t and given by $Y_t^{(u)}$. Correspondingly, $Y_t^{1(u)}$ and $Y_t^{0(u)}$ define an unemployed's potential outcomes if taking up an overeducated job at u and if remaining unemployed at least up to u , respectively.

For each elapsed unemployment duration u the treatment effect of interest is defined as:

$$\Delta_t^u = E\left(Y_t^{1(u)} - Y_t^{0(u)} \mid D^{(u)} = 1\right) = E\left(Y_t^{1(u)} \mid D^{(u)} = 1\right) - E\left(Y_t^{0(u)} \mid D^{(u)} = 1\right)$$

for $t = u, u + 1, \dots, T$

In the following, we will focus on the average of the Δ_t^u to highlight the general trends and patterns in the treatment effects (Sianesi, 2004).⁵ As the second term $E(Y_t^{0(u)} \mid D^{(u)} = 1)$ is unobserved, estimating the effects involves comparing persons who enter overeducation with similar persons who have reached the same elapsed unemployment duration but remain unemployed and continue the job search. Similarity is defined in terms of the propensity score, that is, we only compare individuals who have a similar probability of taking up an overeducated job at time u , given their observed characteristics X . The propensity score is estimated by a discrete-time hazard independent competing risk model taking into account the exit dynamics from unemployment and right-censoring.⁶ Identification rests on the conditional independence assumption (CIA)

$$Y_t^{0(u)} \perp D^{(u)} \mid X = x \text{ for } t = u, u + 1, \dots, T$$

stating that conditional on observed characteristics X and the elapsed unemployment duration u , in the absence of the treatment the treated would experience the same outcome as the controls. In other words, a causal interpretation rests on the strong assumption that we observe all variables that influence both taking up an overeducated job and the respective potential outcomes. The plausibility of this assumption must be discussed in the light of the large number of covariates we control for, including socio-demographics, educational attainment, work biography, characteristics of the last job, and many more. The covariates have been selected theoretically and are measured before the treatment to avoid post-treatment bias. Table 1 reports the definition and measurement of each covariate. For example, controlling for household income or family characteristics adjusts for differences in search constraints. To capture differences in human capital and previous labor market performance, we control

for educational attainment and past and recent labor market experience. In contrast to studies that compare overeducation to adequate employment, our focus on unemployed who have lost their job should reduce both observed and unobserved differences and allows for the adjustment of previous job characteristics. Matching on work biography, previous occupational class and labor income should at least partly control for variables we cannot observe. Specifically, following Sianesi (2004: 138), we think that controlling for the elapsed unemployment duration should also “capture important unobservables” like motivation or readiness for work. However, if both groups differ with respect to unobserved characteristics (e.g., ability) after controlling for these covariates, the differences in outcomes is at least partly due to unobserved heterogeneity.

To balance the treated and controls on X , we form “statistical twins” in terms of the propensity score, that is, the discrete-time hazard. Comparing different matching algorithms, we decided for radius matching with a propensity score radius of 0.01, because it gave the best results with respect to covariate balance. Given its importance, we matched exactly on the elapsed unemployed duration, that is, we only compare treated and controls who have spent the same number of months in unemployment. Accordingly, common support is checked in every month of u . In general, only about two percent of the treated are off-support. Standard errors have been calculated using the variance approximation of Lechner (2001).⁷ All matching analyses are performed using the `psmatch2` ado in Stata (Leuven and Sianesi, 2012).

Table 1 Definition and measurement of the covariates

Covariate	Definition and measurement
<i>Socio-demographics</i>	
Age	In years
Sex	1=female, 0=male
Migration background	1=first or second generation immigrant, 0=otherwise
<i>Education</i>	
Educational attainment	1=vocational degree, 2=technical college degree (former GDR) ^a , 3=university degree
<i>Work biography</i>	
Total employment experience (2 variables)	Total full-time experience in (decimal) years, total part-time experience in (decimal) years
Recent employment experience	Number of months employed in the 12 months before unemployment
Total unemployment experience	Total unemployment experience in (decimal) years
Previous unemployment spells	Total number of previous unemployment spells since the age of 15
Recent unemployment experience	Number of months unemployed in the 12 months before unemployment
<i>Characteristics of last job</i>	
Occupational class	6 categories according to the EGP class classification: 1=higher managerial and professional workers (I), 2=lower managerial and professional workers (II), 3=routine non-manual workers (IIIa, IIIb), 4=self-employed (IVa-IVc), 5=skilled manual workers (VI), 6=unskilled manual workers (VIIa, VIIb)
Labor income	Real monthly net labor income in 1000 Euro (adjusted to 2006 Euros)
Job satisfaction	0=completely dissatisfied, 10=completely satisfied
<i>Household characteristics</i>	
Household income	Real annual equivalized disposable household income in 1000 Euro (adjusted to 2006 Euros)
Partner	3 categories: 1=no partner or spouse in household, 2=partner in household, 3=spouse in household
Children	Number of children from 0 to 14 years

continued on the next page

Table 1 continued*Health*

Health satisfaction 0=completely dissatisfied, 10=completely satisfied
Disability 1=legally attested disability of 30 percent or more, 0=otherwise

Context characteristics

Year spell started 4 categories: 1=1984-1990, 2=1991-1997, 3=1998-2002, 4=2003-2011
Quarter spell started 4 categories: 1=January-March, 2=April-June, 3=July-September, 4=October-December
Region 4 categories according to the recommendation of the SOEP:
1=North-Germany (Bremen, Hamburg, Lower Saxony, Schleswig-Holstein)
2=East-Germany (Berlin, Brandenburg, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt, Thuringia)
3=South-Germany (Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, Hesse)
4=West-Germany (North-Rhine Westphalia, Rhineland-Palatinate, Saarland)
Regional unemployment^b Monthly unemployment rate of the federal state
Unemployment duration 8 categories:
(baseline hazard) 1=1 month, 2=2 months, 3=3 months, 4=4-6 months, 5=7-9 months,
6=10-12 months, 7=13-15 months, 8=16 months or more

Notes: ^a The German name is “Ingenieurs-/Fachschule”, ^b The monthly unemployment rate of the federal state is taken from Statistics of the Federal Employment Agency (2015) and the monthly published official notifications of the Federal Employment Agency (1984-1991) and has been merged to the SOEP.

Source: Own illustration.

4 Results

4.1 Descriptive statistics

To provide an overview of the sample Table 2 displays some descriptive statistics on the number and duration of unemployment spells by exit status. Summary statistics on the covariates at inflow into unemployment are presented in Supplement B. Of the 4,538 unemployment spells, 4,038 spells are completed (89%) and 500 right-censored (11%). Among the completed spells 76% end in employment, 13% in education/training, and 11% in inactivity showing that the majority of the unemployed experience re-employment. However, more than a third of the re-employed end up in jobs for which they are overeducated. Compared to the percentage of overeducated workers in the working population (18%) this highlights the importance of overeducation as a route out of unemployment.⁸ Table 2 also summarizes the duration of the completed spells. On average, unemployment spells that end in adequate employment are about three months shorter than those that end in overeducation emphasizing that an overeducated re-entry may not be relevant to some unemployed, because they find adequate employment before. Accordingly, this implies that it is important to use the dynamic definition of the controls as discussed in the previous section.

Table 2 Duration of completed spells by exit status (in months)

Exit to	Mean	SD	P ₂₅	P ₅₀	P ₇₅	N (spells)
Overeducation	9.4	12.8	2	6	12	1067
Adequate employment	6.1	7.6	2	4	8	2011
Education/training	9.7	11.5	3	6	12	532
Inactive	12.0	13.3	3	8	15	428

Notes: P₂₅ to P₇₅ = 25th to 75th percentile of the distribution.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

4.2 Propensity score matching

The following discussion focuses on a comparison of covariate balance before and after matching to assess the quality of matching. Supplement C reports the results of the discrete-time hazard competing risk model that has been used to estimate the propensity score. Figure 1 summarizes the quality of the radius matching by means of an empirical quantile-quantile plot (Ho *et al.*, 2006). It plots the quantiles of the propensity score distribution of the treated against that of the controls. Before matching, the plot is consistently below the 45-degree line, indicating that the treated are substantially different from the controls. After matching, the distributions of both groups are very similar, suggesting that they have been successfully matched.

--- Figure 1 ---

We also calculated the means and the mean standardized bias before and after matching, to assess the balance on every single covariate (Table 3). Since we matched exactly on unemployment duration, the standardized bias for this variable falls to zero after matching. Table 3 highlights some other interesting differences.⁹ For example, the unemployed who take up an overeducated job are overrepresented among younger workers, males and first or second generation immigrants and are also more likely to have a university degree. They have less total and recent employment experience but are more likely to have been unemployed in the 12 months before the current unemployment spell. Considering the previous job, the treated are less likely to work in higher managerial and professional occupations and are more likely to be manual workers. In addition, their labor and household income is lower than that of the controls. Comparing the mean standardized bias before and after matching, we find that matching reduces the bias below the standard threshold of 5% for each covariate (Caliendo, 2006). This confirms that matching has been successful.

Table 3 Balance of covariates: Means and standardized bias before and after matching

Covariates	Treated	Controls		Standardized bias	
		before	after	before	after
Unemployment duration (baseline hazard)	9.01	14.01	9.01	-33.2	0.0
Age	37.83	38.72	37.73	-9.6	1.1
Age squared	1522.00	1578.10	1513.60	-8.0	1.2
Female	0.48	0.52	0.49	-6.4	-1.4
First or second generation immigrant	0.17	0.11	0.16	15.9	1.7
Vocational degree	0.80	0.88	0.80	-23.7	-0.6
Technical college degree (former GDR)	0.08	0.03	0.07	18.8	1.7
University degree	0.13	0.08	0.13	14.2	-0.5
Total employment experience (full-time)	12.18	12.29	12.21	-1.2	-0.3
Total employment experience (part-time)	1.61	1.75	1.56	-4.0	1.2
Total employment experience (part-time) x Female	1.47	1.47	1.41	-0.2	1.6
Recent employment experience	10.50	10.66	10.54	-5.9	-1.5
Recent employment experience squared	117.11	120.37	117.84	-7.5	-1.7
Total unemployment experience	1.28	1.46	1.24	-8.1	1.6
Total unemployment experience squared	6.42	7.02	5.98	-2.3	1.7
Previous unemployment spells	1.69	1.68	1.65	0.6	2.2
Recent unemployment experience	1.24	1.07	1.19	7.3	2.3
Higher managerial and professional workers	0.04	0.06	0.04	-10.1	-0.9
Lower managerial and professional workers	0.13	0.17	0.14	-11.8	-3.2
Routine non-manual workers	0.21	0.23	0.22	-4.8	-2.3
Self-employed	0.03	0.04	0.03	-5.8	-0.1
Skilled manual workers	0.22	0.21	0.22	3.6	1.1
Unskilled manual workers	0.37	0.29	0.35	17.2	3.9
Labor income	1.07	1.09	1.07	-5.0	-1.5
Labor income squared	1.37	1.56	1.40	-7.8	-1.1
Job satisfaction	6.12	6.10	6.08	0.9	1.8
Household income	15.55	16.39	15.85	-10.0	-3.6
Household income squared	284.53	365.35	299.85	-8.0	-1.5
No partner or spouse	0.30	0.32	0.30	-3.3	1.6
Partner	0.14	0.16	0.14	-4.5	0.1
Spouse	0.56	0.52	0.56	6.3	-1.6
No partner or spouse x Female	0.13	0.15	0.13	-3.6	1.4
Partner x Female	0.07	0.07	0.07	-2.7	-0.6
Spouse x Female	0.29	0.30	0.30	-2.9	-2.3
Children	0.66	0.67	0.65	-1.0	0.6
Health satisfaction	6.94	6.60	6.88	16.1	2.9
Disability	0.02	0.04	0.02	-11.6	-1.9
Spell started in 1984-1990	0.09	0.06	0.10	11.5	-0.7
Spell started in 1991-1997	0.34	0.28	0.34	12.8	0.0
Spell started in 1998-2002	0.22	0.29	0.23	-16.4	-2.0
Spell started in 2003-2011	0.34	0.36	0.33	-4.0	2.2

continued on the next page

Table 3 continued

Spell started in January-March	0.29	0.28	0.29	1.8	-0.4
Spell started in April-June	0.22	0.23	0.22	-3.4	-1.8
Spell started in July-September	0.24	0.26	0.24	-5.8	0.0
Spell started in October-December	0.26	0.23	0.25	7.3	2.2
North-Germany	0.13	0.12	0.13	4.2	1.0
East-Germany	0.49	0.52	0.49	-5.5	1.2
South-Germany	0.22	0.20	0.23	4.9	-1.9
West-Germany	0.16	0.16	0.16	-1.8	-0.4
Regional unemployment	13.12	13.58	13.15	-9.3	-0.7

Notes: The means of the treated that are on-support are reported.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

4.3 Effects of an overeducated re-entry over time

Employment Chances

Figure 2 shows the probability of being employed 6 to 60 months after the treatment (time zero) for those who have taken up an overeducated job (*treated*) and those who have remained unemployed and continued the job search for at least one month (*controls*). The difference between these probabilities represents the treatment effect. The treatment effect is also shown for the two years before the treatment offering a so-called pre-treatment test of selection bias (Hagen, 2004). If selection bias is present, that is, both groups still differ on background characteristics, the pre-treatment effects will differ from zero. However, Figure 2 illustrates that in the 24 months before the treatment the probability of being employed is approximately the same for both groups, indicating that the CIA is plausible.

--- Figure 2 ---

Considering the post-treatment period, we find that 6 months after the treatment 95% of those who experienced an overeducated re-entry are employed compared to 34% of those who have remained unemployed. This translates into a treatment effect of about 61 percentage points. To give a reading example: On average, six months after the treatment the employment chances of those re-entering the labor market in an overeducated job are 61 percentage points higher than of those who remained unemployed. Of course, in the first 12 months after re-employment large effects are not surprising given that the controls remain unemployed for some time by definition.

However, the positive employment effect is persistent, that is, even two to five years after re-employment the effects range between 10 to 20 percentage points. Additional analyses (not shown) reveal that these positive employment effects are to a similar share explained by a

lower unemployment risk and a lower probability of being out of labor force. Looking at employment chances only, these results provide strong support for the stepping stone hypothesis (1a).

Job quality

However, despite the positive employment effects, an overeducated re-entry does not necessarily have to be a stepping stone into adequate employment. Figure 3 shows the treatment effects for the chances of adequate employment over a period of one to five years after re-employment. Note that these analyses only compare treated and controls who are employed in the respective years. In contrast to the positive employment effects, Figure 3 shows that the unemployed who experience an overeducated re-entry face a strong negative effect in terms of chances of adequate employment. One year after re-employment, they have a 40 percentage point lower chance to work in a job that matches their educational qualifications compared to those who remained unemployed. Although the time trend suggests that some workers advance to adequate employment, the negative effects persist up to five years after re-employment, indicating a significant lock-in effect into overeducation. This result is in line with previous studies (Baert *et al.*, 2013; Pollmann-Schult and Büchel, 2004a) showing that an overeducated re-entry delays the transition to adequate employment. It supports the trap hypothesis (1b), demonstrating that exiting unemployment into overeducation is not a stepping stone into adequate employment.

--- Figure 3 ---

Effect heterogeneity

In order to test whether the effects vary by workers' labor market experience and educational qualification (hypotheses 2 and 3) we repeated the analyses for the respective subgroups.

Table 4 and Table 5 report the treatment effects and standard errors for the two outcomes by labor market experience and educational qualification. Supplement D provides the respective figures. With respect to labor market experience, we distinguish workers with up to five years of total experience (early career workers) from workers with more than five years (established workers) of total experience (i.e., employment and unemployment experience). With respect to educational qualification, we distinguish between workers with a vocational degree and those having a university degree where workers with a technical college degree (GDR) are included in the latter subgroup.

The general patterns and trends in the treatment effects closely resemble the results of the main analyses. We find positive employment effects and negative effects for the chance of adequate employment across all subgroups. These findings are, thus, reassuring and consistent with the main effects reported before. Considering the differences in the employment effects, we find slightly higher employment effects for established workers than for early career workers, especially from year three onwards. As for the chances of adequate employment across subgroups, we find very similar effects for early career workers and established workers (Table 4). Taken together these results contradict hypothesis 2 expecting that early-career workers should benefit more from an overeducated re-entry than established workers.¹⁰

How do the effects differ by educational qualification (Table 5)? In terms of employment chances we do not find any economically significant differences between workers with a vocational degree and workers having a university degree. Considering the chance of adequate employment, the analyses reveal a stronger lock-in effect into overeducation for workers with a vocational degree, in particular, in the first four years after re-employment. This finding lends weak support to hypothesis 3, arguing that workers with academic qualifications should benefit more from an overeducated re-entry. However, considering that these differences are small in size and not apparent in all years, hypothesis 3 has to be rejected. In

sum, the results are in line with previous findings by Baert *et al.* (2013) also suggesting that the effects do not vary substantially across different skill groups.

Table 4 Treatment effects: Employment chances and chances of adequate employment over time by labor market experience

Month	Employment chances				Year	Chances of adequate employment			
	<= 5 years labor market experience		> 5 years labor market experience			<= 5 years labor market experience		> 5 years labor market experience	
	TE	SE	TE	SE		TE	SE	TE	SE
6	0.55	0.02	0.61	0.01	1	-0.43	0.04	-0.39	0.02
12	0.34	0.03	0.39	0.01	2	-0.31	0.05	-0.31	0.02
18	0.21	0.03	0.23	0.02	3	-0.31	0.06	-0.31	0.02
24	0.17	0.04	0.18	0.02	4	-0.25	0.06	-0.29	0.03
30	0.12	0.04	0.20	0.02	5	-0.31	0.06	-0.29	0.03
36	0.13	0.04	0.16	0.02					
42	0.11	0.04	0.17	0.02					
48	0.04	0.04	0.13	0.02					
54	0.06	0.04	0.14	0.02					
60	0.05	0.05	0.12	0.02					

Notes: TE: average of the individual treatment effects by elapsed unemployment duration.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

Table 5 Treatment effects: Employment chances and chances of adequate employment over time by educational qualification

Month	Employment chances				Year	Chances of adequate employment			
	Vocational degree		University degree			Vocational degree		University degree	
	TE	SE	TE	SE		TE	SE	TE	SE
6	0.61	0.01	0.58	0.02	1	-0.44	0.02	-0.29	0.03
12	0.38	0.01	0.38	0.03	2	-0.33	0.02	-0.24	0.04
18	0.22	0.02	0.25	0.03	3	-0.32	0.02	-0.27	0.04
24	0.17	0.02	0.21	0.03	4	-0.31	0.03	-0.21	0.05
30	0.18	0.02	0.20	0.03	5	-0.29	0.03	-0.29	0.04
36	0.16	0.02	0.11	0.04					
42	0.17	0.02	0.10	0.04					
48	0.12	0.02	0.13	0.04					
54	0.14	0.02	0.09	0.04					
60	0.11	0.02	0.09	0.04					

Notes: TE: average of the individual treatment effects by elapsed unemployment duration.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

5 Conclusion

This article sought to reveal whether it is better for the unemployed to take up a job for which they are overeducated or to remain unemployed and continue the search for adequate employment. To test the opposing predictions of the stepping stone and trap hypotheses, we examined the effects of an overeducated re-entry on the long-term employment chances and chances of adequate employment. Because it is likely that these effects vary across the unemployed, we also performed subgroup analyses by labor market experience and educational qualification. Using the SOEP (1984-2012), our analyses are based on a dynamic propensity score matching approach comparing unemployed who take up an overeducated job to similar unemployed who continued the job search for at least one month. This dynamic extension of propensity score matching allows avoiding potential bias due to an inappropriate definition of controls and addressing the key methodological issue of selection into overeducation.

The empirical results reveal that taking up an overeducated job is associated with long-run positive employment effects. Even five years after re-employment, the unemployed who take up an overeducated job have a 10 percentage point higher chance to be employed. Taken by itself, this result speaks in favor of the stepping stone hypothesis, suggesting that policy-makers should enforce the acceptance of overeducated jobs. However, looking at the chances of adequate employment, we find strong negative effects ranging from 30 to 40 percentage points. The latter analysis also shows that only a minority of those who take up an overeducated job advance to adequate employment. These results are in line with previous studies (Baert *et al.*, 2013; Pollmann-Schult and Büchel, 2004a), illustrating that an overeducated re-entry is not a stepping stone into adequate employment. More generally, they are also supportive of studies showing that overeducation is not just a temporary problem (e.g., Pollmann-

Schult and Büchel, 2004b). Considering the subgroup analyses, we find that the effects are rather similar for early-career and established workers as well as for workers with a vocational and university degree.

The following limitations should, however, be considered. First, although we used a very homogenous sample and controlled for many observed differences as well as elapsed unemployment duration, our estimates are biased if treated and controls still differ on unobserved characteristics. For example, if the overeducated were less able, we would underestimate the positive employment effect and overestimate the negative effect in terms of adequate employment. Although a pre-treatment test suggests that the selection on observables assumption is reasonable, we cannot rule out the influence of unobserved heterogeneity. However, Baert *et al.* (2013) report similar results taking account of selection on unobservables by using the timing-of-events approach. Against this background, we think it is unlikely that our findings are explained by unobserved heterogeneity. Second, the literature on overeducation has not yet agreed on a standard measurement. Despite using an extension of the standard subjective approach and testing for alternative measurements, measurement error may still be present. Third, the analyses do not allow identifying the relative importance of different mechanisms. Although lower job search intensity appears to be the most likely explanation of the lock-in effect into overeducation, we cannot disentangle different mechanisms empirically. One promising approach to address these questions is the use of field experiments (see Baert and Verhaest, 2014).

What broader conclusions can be drawn from the results? From a policy-point of view, the analyses point to an important trade-off between employment chances and the chances of adequate employment. For this reason, policies that force the unemployed into overeducation, for example, by tightening benefit eligibility or revising regulations for the type of work the jobless have to accept, may cause persistent qualification mismatches that are costly for the

individual and the society as a whole (Baert *et al.*, 2013). To allow for a more targeted design of policies, future research should investigate under which circumstances an overeducated re-entry represents a stepping stone or a trap, respectively. Although this article shows that the effects vary little by labor market experience and educational qualification, it is likely that the above described trade-off turns out to be positive for some unemployed and negative for others. Follow-up studies could examine how the results vary by unemployment duration or the degree of mismatch. The former analysis would, for example, help to estimate the unemployment duration, at which remaining unemployed only has negative effects. In general, changing perspective and asking how overeducation compares to unemployment seems to be a valuable avenue of future research providing a more comprehensive picture on the impact of overeducation on individuals' careers.

Notes

1 Combining the monthly and yearly data results in spells that end in employment (monthly information), but for which no yearly data is available. If a person has multiple spells in between two interviews, we only kept the spell closest to the next interview resulting in a loss of about 4 percent of spells. For 20 percent of spells that end in employment, information is missing, because persons are not working at the time of the interview.

2 Another measurement used in the literature is the realized matches approach (e.g. Verdugo and Verdugo, 1989) defining the level of required education as a one standard-deviation range around the mean level of education within an occupation (here defined by two-digit ISCO). Using a realized-matches approach or the standard subjective approach does not change the main conclusions reported below.

3 Misclassifications are unlikely due to state dependence in educational (mis-)match. In addition, the median time between the unemployment exit and the next yearly interview is only five months. A sensitivity analysis which reduces this median time to three months gives very similar results.

4 In other words, the controls are composed of those still unemployed at u irrespective of what happens later. For example, they may later take up an overeducated job and become treated themselves. Specifically, a person may serve as both treated and control. For example, a person who enters overeducation after six months may be a control to a person who enters overeducation after three months. Because some persons contribute with spells from different periods, they may be treated or become a control after having been treated before. Consequently, the control observations exceed the treatment observations in each month u by far. Multiple spells also result in “within-person matches”, that is, the treatment and matched control observation originate from different spells of the same person. This applies to about 3 percent of the treatment observations. Excluding these treatment observations has no substantial effect on the results.

5 This average is calculated by weighting the individual Δ_t^u by the elapsed unemployment duration distribution of the treated. Note that the causal interpretation pertains to the individual Δ_t^u .

6 The discrete-time hazard model is estimated by using a multinomial logistic regression based on person-month data (Allison, 1982). The four independent competing risks are: overeducated employment, adequate employment, education/training, inactivity. We used a piecewise-constant specification to model the baseline hazard.

7 Bootstrapping turned out to be too time-consuming and Lechner (2002) finds little difference between the approximated and bootstrapped standard errors.

8 The percentage of overeducated workers in the working population has been estimated based on a sample of all workers of age 18 to 54 over the period of 1984-2012 using the SOEP. It is in line with estimates of previous German studies (see Büchel, 2001: 508).

9 We refrain from a comparison to previous studies on the determinants of overeducation, because different measurements (see Verhaest and Omey, 2010), different sample definitions, and their focus on the comparison of overeducation to adequate employment make such a comparison difficult.

10 We also distinguished workers in their early careers and established workers by age. The results are similar to those reported, showing no substantially relevant differences between workers of age 18-29 (early career) and those of age 30-54 (established workers).

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Figure 1 Quantile-quantile plot of the propensity score of the treated and controls

Notes: This plot is based on the outcome “employment chances t+6”. The results are similar for the other outcomes.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

Figure 2 Treatment effects: Employment chances over time (percentage points)

Notes: treated: probability of employment of those taking up an overeducated job, controls: probability of employment of those remaining unemployment and continuing the search, treatment effect (95% CI): average of the individual treatment effects by elapsed unemployment duration and 95% confidence interval.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

Figure 3 Treatment effects: Chances of adequate employment over time (percentage points)

Notes: treatment effect (95% CI): average of the individual treatment effects by elapsed unemployment duration and 95% confidence interval.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

Better overeducated than unemployed?
The short- and long-term effects of an overeducated labor market re-entry

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplement A. Measurement model of overeducation

Job requirement level	Occupational status	Classification with regard to the degree of congruence between job and education		
		Qualification level gained		
		Vocational degree ¹	Engineering, technical school (East Germany)	University or post-secondary technical college degree ²
No special training required/ only a short introduction on the job	Unskilled/ semi-skilled worker	ov	ov	ov
	Skilled worker/ foreman/ master craftsman	*	-	-
	White-collar worker in an unskilled job	ov	ov	ov
	White-collar worker in a skilled job	*	*	*
	White-collar worker in a highly skilled job	-	-	-
	Self-employed person	ov	ov	ov
	Civil servant	-	-	-
A lengthy period of coaching at my place	Unskilled/ semi-skilled worker	ov	ov	ov
	Skilled worker/ foreman/ master craftsman	*	-	-
	White-collar worker in an unskilled job	ov	ov	ov
	White-collar worker in a skilled job	*	*	*
	White-collar worker in a highly skilled job	*	*	*
	Self-employed person	ov	ov	ov
	Civil servant	*	-	-
Attendance at special theoretical or practical courses/ A certificate of vocational training	Unskilled/ semi-skilled worker	*	ov	ov
	Skilled worker/ foreman/ master craftsman	ad	ov	ov
	White-collar worker in an unskilled job	ad	ov	ov
	White-collar worker in a skilled job	ad	ov	ov
	White-collar worker in a highly skilled job	ad	ad / ³ *	ad / ³ *
	Self-employed person	ad	ov	ov
	Civil servant	ad	ad / ³ *	ad / ³ *
Engineering, technical school required (East Germany)	Unskilled/ semi-skilled worker	-	-	-
	Skilled worker/ foreman/ master craftsman	-	-	-
	White-collar worker in an unskilled job	-	*	ov
	White-collar worker in a skilled job	ad	ad	ov
	White-collar worker in a highly skilled job	ad	ad	ad
	Self-employed person	ad	ad	ad
	Civil servant	-	ad	ov
A university or post-sec. technical college degree	Unskilled/ semi-skilled worker	-	-	-
	Skilled worker/ foreman/ master craftsman	-	-	-
	White-collar worker in an unskilled job	-	-	-
	White-collar worker in a skilled job	-	-	*
	White-collar worker in a highly skilled job	ad	ad	ad
	Self-employed person	ad	ad	ad
	Civil servant	-	ad	ad

Notes: ad=adequate employment, ov=overeducation, *=degree of mismatch not clearly determinable, -=implausible combination

1) including: apprenticeship, vocational school, health care school, technical school, civil service training, other training, master craftsman, engineering, technical degree.

2) including: technical college, university, technical university, dissertation, habilitation.

3) Until 1993 respondents are adequately qualified; after 1993 degree of mismatch is not clearly determinable due to changes in the questionnaire.

Source: Own illustration adapted from Büchel and Weißhuhn (1998).

Supplement B. Descriptive statistics at the inflow into unemployment

Covariates	Mean/Percent	SD
Age	36.1	(9.4)
Female	46.8	
First or second generation immigrant	12.9	
Vocational degree	84.9	
Technical college degree (former GDR)	3.3	
University degree	11.8	
Total employment experience (full-time)	11.4	(9.0)
Total employment experience (part-time)	1.6	(3.5)
Recent employment experience	10.7	(2.4)
Total unemployment experience	1.1	(1.9)
Previous unemployment spells	1.5	(1.9)
Recent unemployment experience	0.9	(2.1)
Higher managerial and professional workers	7.3	
Lower managerial and professional workers	17.9	
Routine non-manual workers	20.8	
Self-employed	3.6	
Skilled manual workers	24.0	
Unskilled manual workers	26.4	
Labor income	1.2	(0.6)
Job satisfaction	6.1	(2.5)
Household income	17.4	(9.1)
No partner or spouse	31.6	
Partner	15.9	
Spouse	52.4	
Children	0.6	(0.9)
Health satisfaction	6.8	(2.1)
Disability	3.0	
Spell started in 1984-1990	8.8	
Spell started in 1991-1997	28.2	
Spell started in 1998-2002	24.1	
Spell started in 2003-2011	38.9	
Spell started in January-March	26.6	
Spell started in April-June	21.7	
Spell started in July-September	25.0	
Spell started in October-December	26.8	
North-Germany	13.0	
East-Germany	44.9	
South-Germany	24.2	
West-Germany	17.9	
Regional unemployment	12.7	(5.0)
N (spells)	4538	
N (persons)	3353	

Notes: See Table 1 for a detailed description of the definition and measurement of the covariates.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

Supplement C. Discrete-time hazard competing risk duration model (Average marginal effects multiplied by 100)

Exit to	Overeducation		Adequately employed		Education/training		Inactivity	
	AME x 100		AME x 100		AME x 100		AME x 100	
Ref.: 1 month								
2 months	-0.251	(0.349)	-0.185	(0.501)	0.240	(0.221)	0.167	(0.194)
3 months	0.049	(0.377)	-0.113	(0.533)	-0.029	(0.218)	-0.142	(0.184)
4-6 months	-0.430	(0.302)	-1.402 ***	(0.427)	0.567 ***	(0.199)	0.147	(0.166)
7-9 months	-0.401	(0.333)	-2.522 ***	(0.452)	0.514 **	(0.224)	0.321 *	(0.194)
10-12 months	-0.207	(0.374)	-2.506 ***	(0.496)	0.777 ***	(0.267)	0.632 ***	(0.237)
13-15 months	-0.012	(0.440)	-3.951 ***	(0.510)	0.489 *	(0.297)	0.590 **	(0.277)
16 months or more	-1.218 ***	(0.294)	-5.233 ***	(0.386)	-0.093	(0.185)	0.372 **	(0.183)
Age	-0.041 *	(0.022)	-0.163 ***	(0.033)	-0.034 **	(0.017)	-0.027 *	(0.014)
Female (Ref.: male)	0.132	(0.187)	-1.508 ***	(0.302)	-0.008	(0.165)	0.792 ***	(0.125)
First or second generation immigrant (Ref.: otherwise)	0.855 ***	(0.281)	-1.586 ***	(0.284)	-0.344 **	(0.165)	-0.107	(0.151)
Ref.: Vocational degree								
Technical college degree (former GDR)	5.675 ***	(0.892)	-3.781 ***	(0.356)	0.789 **	(0.355)	-0.724 ***	(0.167)
University degree	4.768 ***	(0.680)	-0.172	(0.403)	0.210	(0.252)	0.485 *	(0.283)
Total employment experience (full-time)	0.044 **	(0.022)	0.043	(0.032)	-0.017	(0.017)	-0.013	(0.014)
Total employment experience (part-time)	-0.183 **	(0.074)	0.082	(0.074)	0.020	(0.035)	-0.048	(0.030)
Recent employment experience	-0.076	(0.086)	-0.469 ***	(0.127)	-0.124 **	(0.060)	-0.100 *	(0.053)
Total unemployment experience	-0.235 ***	(0.090)	-1.228 ***	(0.167)	-0.125	(0.086)	-0.081	(0.062)
Previous unemployment spells	0.133 **	(0.064)	0.517 ***	(0.095)	0.045	(0.055)	-0.070	(0.050)
Recent unemployment experience	0.171 **	(0.076)	-0.407 ***	(0.099)	-0.116 **	(0.047)	-0.076 *	(0.042)
Ref.: Higher managerial and professional workers								
Lower managerial and professional workers	0.846 ***	(0.238)	-1.214 **	(0.591)	0.175	(0.249)	0.464 **	(0.193)
Routine non-manual workers	1.454 ***	(0.259)	-2.377 ***	(0.605)	0.345	(0.262)	0.484 **	(0.195)
Self-employed	0.865 **	(0.372)	-2.746 ***	(0.730)	-0.129	(0.347)	0.802 **	(0.356)
Skilled manual workers	1.768 ***	(0.281)	-1.799 ***	(0.617)	0.200	(0.265)	0.376 *	(0.211)
Unskilled manual workers	2.517 ***	(0.285)	-3.400 ***	(0.601)	-0.058	(0.254)	0.623 ***	(0.207)

continued on the next page

Supplement C. continued

Labor income	-0.303	(0.237)	0.340	(0.259)	0.396 **	(0.159)	-0.003	(0.144)
Job satisfaction	-0.025	(0.034)	0.089 *	(0.047)	-0.098 ***	(0.023)	0.004	(0.021)
Household income	-0.039 **	(0.018)	0.075 ***	(0.017)	0.041 ***	(0.012)	0.002	(0.008)
Ref.: No partner or spouse								
Partner	0.318	(0.250)	0.756 **	(0.313)	-0.141	(0.178)	0.158	(0.141)
Spouse	0.578 ***	(0.209)	1.346 ***	(0.288)	-0.097	(0.161)	0.487 ***	(0.132)
Children	-0.134	(0.107)	-0.402 ***	(0.147)	-0.005	(0.079)	-0.082	(0.074)
Health satisfaction	0.164 ***	(0.042)	0.157 ***	(0.057)	-0.024	(0.028)	-0.066 ***	(0.025)
Disability	-1.249 ***	(0.329)	-1.342 **	(0.525)	-0.181	(0.288)	1.005 ***	(0.388)
Ref. Spell started in 1984-1990								
Spell started in 1991-1997	-0.669 *	(0.405)	-0.920 **	(0.425)	0.743 ***	(0.242)	-0.501 **	(0.233)
Spell started in 1998-2002	-1.353 ***	(0.408)	-0.047	(0.450)	0.570 **	(0.250)	-0.541 **	(0.237)
Spell started in 2003-2011	-1.037 ***	(0.394)	0.253	(0.424)	-0.371 *	(0.217)	-0.301	(0.231)
Ref.: Spell started in January-March								
Spell started in April-June	-0.160	(0.231)	-0.446	(0.307)	-0.018	(0.155)	0.320 **	(0.140)
Spell started in July-September	-0.400 *	(0.215)	-0.876 ***	(0.287)	0.233	(0.158)	0.237 *	(0.131)
Spell started in October-December	-0.024	(0.227)	0.068	(0.309)	0.061	(0.161)	0.401 ***	(0.148)
Ref.: North-Germany								
East-Germany	-0.192	(0.348)	-0.090	(0.495)	0.469 *	(0.256)	-0.609 **	(0.239)
South-Germany	0.031	(0.331)	-0.745 *	(0.394)	-0.078	(0.200)	1.079 ***	(0.402)
West-Germany	-0.331	(0.301)	-0.918 **	(0.379)	-0.045	(0.196)	0.651 **	(0.274)
Regional unemployment	-0.052	(0.034)	-0.120 **	(0.047)	-0.016	(0.025)	0.088 ***	(0.023)
N (person-months)	40888							
N (spells)	4538							
N (persons)	3353							

Notes: Standard errors in parentheses; *** p<0.05, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10; AME and SE are multiplied by 100; Variables specified with quadratic terms are represented by one AME (Age, recent employment experience, Total unemployment experience, Labor income, household income); Coefficients of interactions are not displayed (Female x Total employment experience (part-time), Female x Partner).

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

Supplement D. Figures for effect heterogeneity analyses (Table 4 and Table 5)

Figure D1. Treatment effects: Employment chances over time by labor market experience (percentage points)

Figure D2. Treatment effects: Chances of adequate employment over time by labor market experience (percentage points)

Notes: Treatment effect: average of the individual treatment effects by elapsed unemployment duration, see Table 4 for the treatment effects and standard errors.

Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.

Figure D3. Treatment effects: Employment chances over time by educational qualification (percentage points)

Figure D4. Treatment effects: Chances of adequate employment over time by educational qualification (percentage points)

Notes: Treatment effect: average of the individual treatment effects by elapsed unemployment duration, see Table 5 for the treatment effects and standard errors.
 Source: SOEP 1984-2012, own calculations.